

Marketing

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**Transformation of marketing communications under the influence of social
media evolution**

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Abstract. The rapid digitalization of economic activity and the widespread adoption of online platforms have significantly reshaped the system of brand–audience interaction. Networked environments, algorithm-driven feeds, and data-based targeting tools have altered the logic of value promotion, shifting emphasis toward interactivity, personalization, and continuous feedback. These processes necessitate a comprehensive examination of the structural and functional changes in contemporary communication systems, influenced by the development of social networking platforms. **The purpose of this study** is to systematize the key directions of modernization in promotional instruments amid the expansion of digital platforms and to substantiate transformations in interaction models between businesses and target audiences driven by content algorithmization and user participation. **Methods.** The research applies general scientific and specialized approaches, including analysis and synthesis to refine the conceptual framework, comparative assessment to identify distinctions between traditional and digital formats of promotion, a structural–functional approach to determine the components of the updated interaction system, and generalization of empirical evidence reflecting current

business practices in digital environments. **Results.** The findings demonstrate a transition from one-way information delivery to multidirectional dialogue with audiences. It is established that the contemporary promotion system is characterized by personalized messaging, the integration of data analytics, the dominance of visual and short-form formats, and the active involvement of consumers in content creation. Algorithmic ranking mechanisms are shown to influence campaign planning and require continuous performance monitoring. The competitiveness of enterprises increasingly depends on their ability to adapt strategic decisions to the dynamics of digital ecosystems and evolving user expectations. **Conclusions.** The study confirms the emergence of an integrated interaction model combining analytical tools, creative formats, and automated message customization technologies. Further development of promotional practices is associated with deeper personalization, broader adoption of artificial intelligence solutions, and enhanced behavioral data analytics.

Keywords: digital platforms, promotion instruments, content algorithmization, personalized messaging, interactive engagement, branding strategy, behavioral analytics.

Трансформація маркетингових комунікацій під впливом еволюції соціальних мереж

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Анотація. Цифровізація суспільних процесів та стрімке поширення онлайн-платформ зумовили докорінні зміни у способах взаємодії підприємств із цільовими аудиторіями. Віртуальні спільноти, алгоритмічні стрічки та інструменти персоналізації сформували нову логіку просування товарів і

послуг, де перевага надається інтерактивності, швидкості обміну повідомленнями та орієнтації на поведінкові дані користувачів. Зазначене актуалізує потребу комплексного осмислення структурних і функціональних змін у системі просування товарів і послуг, зумовлених розвитком мережевих платформ. **Метою** дослідження є систематизація напрямів модернізації інструментарію просування в умовах поширення цифрових платформ, а також обґрунтування змін у моделях взаємодії брендів з аудиторіями під впливом алгоритмізації контенту та зростання ролі користувацької участі. **Методи.** У процесі роботи застосовано загальнонаукові та спеціальні підходи, зокрема аналіз і синтез для уточнення понятійного апарату, порівняння для виявлення відмінностей між традиційними та мережевими форматами просування, структурно-функціональний підхід для визначення складових оновленої системи взаємодії з аудиторіями, а також узагальнення емпіричних даних щодо практики використання цифрових інструментів у підприємницькій діяльності. **Результати.** Встановлено, що розвиток мережевих сервісів спричинив перехід від односторонньої передачі інформації до багатовекторного діалогу з аудиторією. Обґрунтовано, що ключовими характеристиками сучасної системи просування є персоналізація повідомлень, інтеграція аналітики великих масивів даних, домінування візуальних і коротких форматів, активне залученням споживачів до створення контенту. Доведено, що алгоритмічне ранжування матеріалів змінює підходи до планування кампаній та зумовлює необхідність постійного моніторингу показників ефективності. Визначено, що конкурентоспроможність суб'єктів господарювання залежить від здатності адаптувати стратегії просування до динаміки цифрового середовища та очікувань споживачів. **Висновки.** Узагальнення отриманих результатів свідчить про формування нової інтегрованої моделі взаємодії з аудиторіями, яка поєднує аналітичні інструменти, креативні формати та технології автоматизованого налаштування повідомлень. Подальший розвиток інструментів просування

пов'язаний із поглибленням персоналізації, інтеграцією штучного інтелекту та розширенням можливостей аналітики поведінкових даних.

Ключові слова: цифрові платформи, інструменти просування, алгоритмізація контенту, персоналізація повідомлень, інтерактивна взаємодія, брендинг, поведінкова аналітика.

Problem statement. The rapid development of the digital environment and the spread of network platforms have led to profound changes in the way business entities interact with target audiences. Traditional approaches to the formation and implementation of marketing communications lose effectiveness amid content algorithmization, the growing role of user activity, and increased requirements for message personalization. In the modern environment, brands operate in a constant state of information overload, which complicates attracting and retaining consumer attention.

Despite the significant number of scientific works devoted to digital marketing and the development of social networks, the issues of comprehensively understanding the transformation of marketing communications as a complete system under the influence of evolving network platforms remain insufficiently systematized. Changes in the functional characteristics of communication tools, mechanisms for building trust in the brand, and models of interaction with audiences, in terms of interactivity and two-way exchange of information, require clarification.

The problem becomes especially urgent due to the need to adapt promotional strategies to dynamic changes in the digital space, the introduction of analytical data-processing technologies, and the use of automated message customization tools. Solving the outlined issues is directly related to the practical tasks of enhancing enterprise competitiveness, optimizing promotional costs, and building long-term customer relationships.

Thus, there is a need for theoretical justification and practical understanding of the processes of transformation in marketing communications under the influence of the evolution of social networks, which determine the direction of further research and meet the modern requirements for the development of the economy and society.

Analysis of recent research and publications. The problems of the transformation of marketing communications in the digital environment and the influence of social networks on consumer behavior are actively covered in modern scientific publications. Thus, V. Maslianchuk [1] emphasizes that integrating digital tools into business ecosystems increases the effectiveness of partner interactions and creates new communication models. Y. Hrushko [2; 3] notes the role of intelligent technologies in the development of creative advertising concepts for fast moving consumer goods and the adaptation of brand messages when entering European Union markets, which ensures the relevance of communication strategies.

Research by V. Levit [4] demonstrates the influence of ESG-oriented strategies in organizing large-scale events on the formation of the territory's brand value, underscoring the importance of social responsibility in digital communication. I. Poruchynska [5] notes that the use of communication tools in the promotion of goods, illustrated by the Nike brand, allows for increased recognition and the formation of a consistent branded image in the digital environment.

Y. Zhu [6], using the example of Starbucks, emphasizes the importance of holistic social media marketing strategies to achieve digital brand success, and L. Wang [7] demonstrates the effectiveness of using TikTok in increasing engagement and interaction with the Coca-Cola audience. At the same time, V. Herasymchuk and Y. Lyzhova [8] highlight the specifics of Instagram marketing tools, emphasizing the need to adapt content to the platform's algorithmic mechanisms.

Scientific research by J. M. Alcántara-Pilar et al. [9] examined the impact of influencer authority on purchase intentions on TikTok, highlighting the importance of personalized, targeted messages in shaping users' behavioral responses.

Z. Tiahunova et al. [10] demonstrate that digital marketing strategies of trade enterprises on social media platforms increase the effectiveness of interaction with users and provide data integration for planning activities.

Scientists A. A. Adwan and G. Altrjman [11] investigate the role of social networks in the development of sustainable branding strategies, while S. I. Al-Ayed and A. A. Al-Tit [12] analyze the impact of digital customer behavior on performance through integrated CRM systems. S. Alvin and A. Yasmin [13] emphasize the importance of digital marketing activities for promoting brands in both local and global markets.

The publication by N. Babko, I. Naumenko, and S. Spivak [14] outlines the key aspects of marketing communications in information networks, in particular, content management and audience interaction. Author M. Konopliannikova [15] examines influencer marketing, emphasizing its role in building trust and user engagement in social media.

The generalization of the data from these publications shows that digital technologies and social networks radically change the structure and functions of marketing communications, stimulate the personalization of content, interactive engagement, and the use of analytical data to evaluate effectiveness.

Highlighting previously unresolved parts of the overall problem. Therefore, the processing of scientific sources demonstrates the researchers' focus on the characteristics of individual digital tools of promotion and on their applied aspects. At the same time, there is a lack of a general conceptual model that reflects the transformation of marketing communications as a complete system in the context of the development of network platforms. The internal structure of the communication complex, the logic of interaction among its components, and the functional reorientation of traditional elements in the digital environment require clarification.

Scientific understanding of the strategic adaptation of communication activities to algorithmic mechanisms of content ranking and personalization remains

limited. Most of the works describe the technical capabilities of the platforms. Still, the question of the long-term impact of automated message settings on trust, loyalty, and audience behavioral responses remains only partially addressed. Changes in the models of interaction between brands and users in terms of interactivity and co-creation require in-depth analysis.

Methodical support for evaluating the effectiveness of integrated audience interaction has also not reached a sufficient level of systematization. The lack of unified approaches to measuring indicators of involvement, reputational capital, and the client's long-term value makes it difficult to make informed management decisions. It impedes the formulation of strategic guidelines for enterprise development.

These aspects are fundamentally important for a deep understanding of the patterns of development of marketing communications in the modern digital space, as they determine the potential for creating competitive advantages and sustainable relationships with audiences. The study of these issues will clarify the theoretical foundations of modernizing the communication complex and develop practical recommendations for adapting strategies to the evolving conditions of social networks.

Formulation of the article goals (statement of the task). The purpose of the article is to conduct a comprehensive study of the transformation of marketing communications driven by the evolution of social networks and to identify key changes in the structure, content, and interaction tools between enterprises and target audiences in the digital environment.

Achieving the set goal involves the following main tasks:

- to investigate the essence and structural characteristics of marketing communications taking into account the development of social networks and digital technologies;

- to determine the factors that lead to changes in the functioning of the communication complex and influence the behavior of audiences in the online space;

- to justify directions for improving the communication activities of enterprises in order to increase the effectiveness of interaction with users of network platforms.

Presentation of the main research material. The spread of digital technologies and social networks is radically transforming the nature of interaction between enterprises and target audiences. The use of content ranking algorithms, message personalization, and interactive communication formats fundamentally changes the conditions for product and service promotion, making traditional marketing methods increasingly ineffective. Under these conditions, companies are forced to adapt their communication strategies to the dynamic nature of the digital environment and the behavioral characteristics of consumers.

Today, online platforms enable multi-vector interaction with audiences and accelerate the exchange of information, which raises questions about trust in the brand, user involvement, and the effectiveness of communication messages. Therefore, there is an objective need for a comprehensive study of the transformations of marketing communications, the identification of factors driving changes in the functions and structure of the communication complex, and the evaluation of the effectiveness of new formats of interaction between enterprises and target audiences.

In the context of these changes, the influence of social networks and digital platforms on the very mechanism of communication interaction is of particular importance. If earlier information flows were mostly one-way and directed from the enterprise to the consumer, then the modern digital environment provides a continuous two-way exchange of messages, in which users are not only recipients of information but also active participants in its creation, distribution, and interpretation. Such a transformation of the communication model leads to changes in approaches to demand formation, reputation maintenance, and audience attraction, which increasingly depend on enterprises' ability to adapt content to

users' behavioral characteristics, respond promptly to changes in their interests, and systematically use digital analytical data.

Under these conditions, the structure of marketing communications becomes complex, with the informational component encompassing the creation and distribution of content in various formats, thereby personalizing messages and enhancing their perception by the audience. At the same time, the organizational element involves coordinating communication activities, defining target segments, and planning campaigns that account for the specifics of the digital environment and user behavior. In turn, the analytical component includes the systematic collection, processing, and interpretation of data on audience behavior, the level of its involvement, and the effectiveness of communication actions [3], which enables justified adjustment of promotion strategies and increases their effectiveness.

Currently, digital technologies are significantly transforming the functional characteristics of enterprises' communication systems, changing not only the tools for interacting with audiences but also the principles of managing communication processes. Under such conditions, the importance of flexible content management, support for continuous dialogue with users, and adaptation of messages to the algorithmic mechanisms of digital platforms is increasing. Therefore, the effectiveness of marketing communications in the modern environment is determined not by the isolated use of individual channels, but by their consistent functioning and the ability to exert a complex influence on user behavior [4].

The practical dimension of these transformations is most clearly manifested in the communication strategies of leading international brands. In particular, on Instagram, Nike implements an approach that combines personalized messages with interactive user engagement through content [5]. The use of specialized digital tools that allow subscribers to create individual sneaker designs not only increases audience engagement but also fosters a sense of participation in the product's creation, thereby strengthening brand loyalty.

Similar trends can be seen in other industries, particularly in gastronomy, where digital platforms serve as a space for joint interaction between the brand and the consumer. In its own mobile applications and social networks, Starbucks implements mechanisms that encourage users to share their own recipes, rate new products, and participate in interactive promotions [6, p. 189]. Such a communication model not only provides information to the audience but also stimulates its active participation in shaping the consumer experience, increasing the frequency of repeat interactions and strengthening the emotional connection with the brand.

An important role in the transformation of marketing communications is played by the algorithmic mechanisms of digital platforms, which determine the logic of content distribution and its coverage. In particular, on the TikTok platform, recommendation algorithms prioritize content that demonstrates high user activity, thereby significantly expanding the audience for viewing it [7, p. 382]. As a result, businesses focus on creating short dynamic videos with interactive elements, surveys and challenges that stimulate user engagement and increase the viral potential of communication messages.

Further deepening of interaction between brands and consumers occurs within digital communities formed around users shared interests and supported by continuous feedback tools. An illustrative example is LEGO's activity on Reddit and Discord, which creates an environment for sharing user projects, discussing ideas, and participating in thematic competitions [16]. This communication format is not limited to informing the audience; it creates a space for co-creation, in which users are active participants in the communication process. As a result, trust in the brand is strengthened, a sense of community among users is strengthened, and the likelihood of repeat purchases and the formation of long-term loyalty increases.

Summarizing the given examples, marketing communications in the digital environment acquire the features of personalization, interactivity and behavioral adaptability. Under these conditions, the effectiveness of communication campaigns

is determined not only by the volume of disseminated information but above all by the level of user participation, the speed of message circulation, and the audience's readiness to create and distribute joint content.

The specified transformations of the communication complex are caused by a fusion of technological, social, and behavioral factors that mutually reinforce one another. Algorithmic mechanisms of social network platforms determine the visibility of content and the structure of information flows, actually influencing the distribution of audience attention. Posts that generate higher user interaction are emphasized in news feeds, encouraging businesses to create content with pronounced engaging features and high engagement potential.

Thus, personalizing communications becomes a key tool for adapting marketing messages to the individual needs and interests of the audience. Digital platforms accumulate significant amounts of data on user behavior, preferences, and interactions with content, enabling detailed audience segmentation and the formulation of targeted communication strategies. Increasing the level of personalization, in turn, transforms consumer expectations regarding the relevance, timeliness, and value of the information received, which forces enterprises to constantly improve their approaches to content management.

At the same time, the growth of the role of interactivity changes the very nature of communication, transforming it from an informational influence to a process of participation. Polls, challenges, polls, contests, and the ability to create custom content activate audiences, strengthen two-way connections, and increase engagement. Instagram, TikTok, and Discord platforms provide advanced tools for implementing such forms of interaction [8, p. 643], which directly affect audience behavior and their willingness to participate in promotional activities.

The speed of information exchange and the continuity of digital communications form another dimension of the transformation of the functions of the marketing communication complex. In the context of constant platform availability, users expect prompt responses from brands to comments, requests, and

reviews, which drives the implementation of real-time monitoring and analytics systems. Timely collection and processing of data on the nature of audience interaction with content creates the basis for adapting messages, increasing their relevance, and optimizing communication strategies.

At the same time, behavioral and social factors determine the mechanisms of information dissemination in the digital environment and the formation of a viral effect. Users tend to actively distribute content that corresponds to their interests and value orientations, which is increasing the role of organic message distribution. This increases the value of the brand's reputational equity and establishes two-way communication as a central element of the modern marketing strategy.

To generalize the practical manifestations of these trends, table 1 presents examples of enterprise communication strategies that demonstrate the impact of technological, behavioral, and social factors on the effectiveness of audience interaction.

Table 1

Examples of using marketing communications in a digital environment

Enterprise	Digital platform	Communication format	The main purpose	Influence on the behavior of the audience
Nike	Instagram	Personalized sneaker design tools and interactive content	Attracting and increasing consumer loyalty	Users create their own content and interact with the brand, and long-term cooperation
Starbucks	Mobile app, Instagram, Facebook	Encouragement to share your own drink recipes, evaluate new products, and participate in interactive promotions	Maintaining interest and encouraging repeat contacts	User engagement increases repeat interactions with the brand and builds community
Red Bull	TikTok	Short videos with interactive elements and challenges	Increasing reach and viral content	Stimulates active user participation and organic distribution of content
LEGO	Reddit, Discord	User communities, contests and project discussions	Attracting and receiving feedback from consumers	Builds trust in the brand and encourages repeat purchases

Enterprise	Digital platform	Communication format	The main purpose	Influence on the behavior of the audience
Coca-Cola	Facebook, Instagram	Analysis of audience reactions to content and adaptation of communications	Adjustment of advertising campaigns	Increases the relevance of messages and the effectiveness of interaction
Adidas	YouTube, Instagram	Video series with interactive challenges and user participation	Expanding the audience	Users join challenges, audience activity and brand recognition increase

Source: compiled by the author based on [5; 6 p. 189; 7, p. 383; 8, p. 643; 9; 16]

The analysis of the given examples of marketing communications allows us to identify the key factors driving the transformation of the communication complex in the digital environment. First of all, it is the personalization of content, which ensures the relevance of messages to specific audience segments and stimulates user interaction with the brand. At the same time, interactive communication formats, such as polls, contests, video challenges, and the creation of custom content, increase audience activity and foster an emotional connection with consumers. In addition, the algorithmic ranking of content on the platforms determines the order in which messages appear in users' feeds. It significantly affects the reach of target audiences, and user behavior analytics enables prompt adjustments to communication strategies, increasing the effectiveness of campaigns.

Different social media channels perform specific functions within an overall promotion strategy. For example, Instagram focuses on visual messages and brand image formation, while TikTok enables rapid viral spread and stimulates interaction through trending formats [9]. The combination of these factors creates the conditions for dynamic management of the company's communication system, allowing the adaptation of messages to users' behavioral characteristics and the integration of different platforms into a single promotion strategy.

Changes in the functioning of the marketing communication complex are directly correlated with the transformation of audience behavior under the influence

of technological, social and behavioral components of the digital environment. Under these conditions, developing a content strategy to increase users' emotional and cognitive involvement becomes important [10, p. 512]. Special attention is paid here to optimizing messages to stimulate audience interaction and active participation, which fosters a positive perception of the brand, strengthens loyalty, and contributes to the long-term effectiveness of communication campaigns.

The speed of content adaptation to changes in user interests is a critical factor in the effectiveness of marketing communications in the digital environment. Analytical platforms allow monitoring the current priorities of the audience, determining optimal publication intervals, and adjusting messages promptly [11, p. 446]. This provides a personalized interaction with users, increases trust in the brand, builds loyalty, and stimulates repeat consumer contact with the product or service.

In turn, the introduction of algorithmic mechanisms of platforms significantly affects audience coverage and the effectiveness of communication campaigns. Recommender systems, automated targeting and ranking algorithms align messages with the specifics of each channel, ensure consistency in the communication strategy, and maximize the effectiveness of marketing activities.

So, the dynamics of user behavior are shaped by the intersection of visual content, interactive elements, and social confirmation through likes, comments, and reposts. The combination of these factors stimulates audience participation, strengthens the emotional and cognitive connection with the brand, and allows for the evaluation of the effectiveness of individual tools within the complex.

The expansion of digital platforms creates conditions for the emergence of new models of consumer behavior, in particular, the active creation and distribution of content by users themselves. The task of modern marketing strategies is to ensure two-way communication, integrate information from different market segments, and coordinate actions across all digital channels, which maximizes audience involvement and increases the effectiveness of interaction with the brand.

As shown in fig. 1, digital platforms are a central element of the structure of marketing communications, determining the channels of interaction and influencing audience behavior.

Fig. 1. The structure of digital marketing communications on digital platforms and their impact on audience behavior

Source: compiled by the author

Therefore, digital platforms are the basis for transforming the interaction between brands and their audiences in the digital environment. Personalization of content supports the relevance of messages for different user segments, interactivity stimulates two-way interaction and active audience participation, and algorithmic optimization and analytics enable evaluating the effectiveness of campaigns and quickly adjusting strategies. The joint action of these elements increases user engagement, builds trust in the brand and strengthens consumer loyalty.

Based on an analysis of key factors in the transformation of digital marketing communications, it is possible to identify areas for improving enterprises' activities to increase the effectiveness of their interaction with users. To ensure the relevance

of messages, it is recommended to implement dynamic content adjustment systems that account for changes in the audience's interests and behavior and allow for quickly updating the format and topic of publications.

Interactive elements of communication campaigns should be planned with an emphasis on creating a two-way dialogue with users, including surveys, contests, live broadcasts and personalized messages. This increases audience engagement and helps build trust in the brand.

Analytical tools must be integrated into the communication management process to monitor message effectiveness in real time, evaluate conversions and user interactions, and quickly adjust promotion strategies. Special attention is paid to cross-platform content coordination, which involves synchronizing publications, coordinating advertising campaigns, and maintaining a single brand image across various social networks.

To effectively manage these processes, it is recommended to form specialized teams responsible for monitoring the digital environment, analyzing trends, and managing content in real time. Such measures will help increase the effectiveness of communication campaigns, strengthen relationships with users, and adapt strategies to the dynamic conditions of the online space.

Conclusions. Analysis of the transformation of marketing communications in the digital environment showed that interaction with the audience through personalized content, interactive formats and algorithmic analytics forms an effective communication system capable of increasing user engagement and strengthening brand trust. Coordinated use of multiple platforms and continuous tracking of results creates a transparent campaign management mechanism that allows for quickly adapting strategies to changing audience interests and maintaining a consistent company image.

Integration of analytical data and continuous monitoring of user behavior enables timely adjustments to messages and the optimization of communication resources. It is found that systematic work with platform algorithms, analysis of the

effectiveness of content formats, and coordination of cross-platform activities increase interaction effectiveness and foster sustainable audience loyalty.

Further research could focus on developing quantitative indicators to evaluate the effectiveness of digital communications, predicting user behavior using big data analytics, and optimizing cross-platform interactions to enhance the effectiveness of marketing strategies.

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